

immerse

INTEGRATION MAPPING OF REFUGEE
AND MIGRANT CHILDREN

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IMMERSE DELIVERABLE D4.1

COLLECTION OF GOOD PRACTICES AT THE NATIONAL AND EU LEVEL

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Summary

This report is the outcome of the Work Package 4 encompassing the collection and analysis of 60 good practices on migrant and refugee children's socio-educational integration across Europe. The comparative analysis and the in-depth analysis of 12 case-studies provide an interesting overview of local, national and European initiatives aimed at migrant and refugee children's socio-educational inclusion, and contribute to the development of a set of recommendations addressed to decision makers and the educational sector.

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COLLECTION OF GOOD PRACTICES AT NATIONAL AND EU LEVEL

1 Executive Summary

The present report is the outcome of IMMERSE project Work Package 4, encompassing the collection and analysis of good practices on migrant and refugee children's socio-educational integration. IMMERSE research partners collected 60 good practices across Europe that were evaluated through a comparative analysis. The findings of this comparison and the in-depth analysis of 12 case studies are reported here to provide a wealth of contextualised data and cross-cutting features regarding the landscape of implemented or ongoing socio-educational initiatives targeting migrant and refugee children in Europe. The production and study of this rich set of good practices, together with the results of other IMMERSE research activities, is aimed at the development of a set of recommendations and advocacy initiatives to be implemented in order to achieve political and educational change at the national and EU level in the field of migrant and refugee children's socio-educational inclusion.

The report is organized as follows: following the executive summary, Section 2 briefly introduces IMMERSE project's objectives and especially the aim and content of WP4. Following this, section 3 provides an overview of the methodology adopted, focusing on the quality criteria, approaches and areas of interest considered, and the process followed to develop this report. Section 4 shows the comparative analysis of the selected 60 good practices, offering a comprehensive overview of their features and an in-depth analysis of the key findings related to seven areas of interest: integration outcomes, monitoring and evaluation, expertise and professionalism, networks and partnerships, communication and dissemination, reproducibility and transferability, and funds and resources. The subsequent section includes the extended description of 12 selected case studies in order to present a variety of inspirational initiatives that can shape ideas on how to address the inclusion of children with a migrant background in European societies. In conclusion, some considerations and first reflections about policy recommendations addressed to the educational and policy sector are proposed to promote political and educational change at national and EU levels.

The takeaways are summarized below:

multidimensional approach to mirror the complexity of socio-educational integration processes through a combination of activities, multiple targets and extended spaces of intervention

multi-level approach to properly and comprehensively foster the goal of inclusion

multi-stakeholder, interdisciplinary and collaborative approach to ensure a high-level, qualified, and effective intervention

innovative intercultural education practices based on the adoption of an integrated, tailor-made, empowering, inclusive and participatory approach

transfer, systematization and capitalization of the know-how, and sharing of best and innovative practices to reinforce a common model of integration, based on a balance between standardization and flexibility

adequate funds and resources should also be allocated to guarantee the sustainability and the systematization of good practices

2 IMMERSE Project: Good Practices Collection and Analysis

The “**Integration Mapping of Refugee and Migrant Children in Schools and Other Experiential Environments in Europe**” – IMMERSE project is a research initiative that began in December 2018 and was funded by the Horizon2020 Programme of the European Commission.

The IMMERSE project emerges at a time when Europe and its socio-educational system are under immense pressure due to the increased and diverse migration flows and the current refugee crisis. **Children in immigration contexts are one of the most vulnerable groups** facing specific needs and obstacles and, thus, require appropriate protection and guarantees that their human rights will be upheld as enshrined in international covenants and acknowledged by Europe and its member states.

Migration flows undoubtedly pose challenges for receiving countries. The situation especially impacts national education systems since they need to embrace growing cultural, linguistic, socio-economic, and ethnic diversity. **Effective education and social policies are necessary to successfully integrate migrant children into society**¹ (OECD, 2018a) and unlock the benefits of migration, including a more open and culturally diverse society, improved social progress, and economic innovation.

In this framework, **IMMERSE aims to map and enhance the socio-educational inclusion of refugee and migrant children in schools and other learning experiential environments in Europe in order to foster the construction of inclusive and cohesive societies.**

This report is the outcome of the work package 4 (WP4) of the IMMERSE project, encompassing the collection and analysis of good practices on migrant and refugee children’s socio-educational integration carried out at the local, national, and regional levels. IMMERSE research partners **collected 60 good practices across several European countries**, which were evaluated through a comparative analysis. The findings of this comparison are here reported to provide a wealth of contextualised data and cross-cutting features regarding the landscape of implemented or ongoing socio-educational initiatives targeting migrant and refugee children in Europe. This report further includes the extended description of **12 selected case studies** to display a variety of inspirational initiatives that can shape ideas on how to address the inclusion of children with a migratory background in European societies.

The production and study of this rich set of good practices, together with the results of the other IMMERSE qualitative and quantitative research activities, is aimed at the **development of a set of recommendations and advocacy initiatives to be implemented in order to achieve political and educational change at the national and EU level.**

Through the publication and dissemination of this report, the partners of IMMERSE additionally intend to provide the possibility for operators, decision-makers, the educational sector, and the wider public to **learn more about positive, innovative, and effective practices for the socio-educational inclusion of migrant and refugee children.** In this regard, the initiatives identified through the process are included in the IMMERSE Online Digital Database to encourage the dissemination of good examples and foster their replicability and advancement in other educational environments. The results of this report will be presented

¹ OECD. (2018a). The Resilience of Students with an Immigrant Background. Summary for Germany. Paris: OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9789264292093-en>

Deliverable 4.1 Collection of good practices (national and EU level)

at the national events that will be held in the partners' countries and during the final conference, where a series of recommendations will also be proposed.

3 Methodology

3.1 What Is a Good Practice?

The notion of *good practice* commonly indicates a novel and creative solution aimed at improving the living conditions of individuals, groups, and communities. It is a successful experience that has been tested and validated and which can produce benefits in the medium/long term. Good practices are initiatives that can be subject to a mainstreaming process and be transposed to different contexts. Overall, within the EU frame and definitions, there are a variety of nuances to the idea of good practice. However, there is a common thread in targeting “**strategies, approaches and/or activities that have been shown through research and evaluation to be effective, efficient, sustainable and/or transferable, and to reliably lead to the desired result.**”²

However, a practice can be said to be “good” only relative to a **specific context of reference** and to its capacity to respond to a **specific need**. Moreover, it is important to make **explicit normative stances and methodological choices** when working on good practices. For this reason, any absolutism in evaluating a good practice (e.g., nominating it as *best practice*) was here avoided, as it constitutes an obstacle concerning the possibility of learning from it, replicating certain traits, and adapting others to new cases and contexts.

3.1.1 Quality Criteria for a Good Practice

Considering that integration constitutes a dynamic two-way process with many interrelated dimensions (legal, economic, social, cultural, educational, etc.) and acting at different levels (individuals, institutions, social systems), the set of normative and empirical features to take into account in the investigation of good practices is, in turn, complex and multifaceted.

In accordance with the relevant literature and the most common features recurring in the EU policy frameworks, in the IMMERSE project, the following identification requirements for a good practice are taken into account:

Efficacy	Efficiency
<p><i>The capacity to achieve the objectives as attested by rigorous validation and evaluation of the results.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Correspondence between the practices’ purposes and the outcomes identified in the IMMERSE Dashboard of indicators. ✓ Potential to increase the social capital and foster the empowerment of stakeholders and targets (e.g., access to networks and communities; commitment to the community’s well-being). 	<p><i>The adequate use of resources to achieve the set objectives.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Means-ends consistency. ✓ Internal organization and reflexivity (professional resources, disposition to learning by doing, team working, etc.). ✓ Partnerships activated and characters of the overall governance (e.g., participation and inclusiveness of stakeholders).

² <https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/index.cfm?action=furl.go&go=/what-are-good-practices>

Reproducibility & Transferability	Political relevance
<p><i>The potential of interventions to be replicated in similar and/or different contexts, respectively.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Availability of communication tools to promote the effective transfer of experiences and methodologies. ✓ Identification of paths and processes necessary for transferability (e.g., human resources, training, structures and equipment, costs, etc.). ✓ Identification of the risks and mitigation possibilities in transferring the practice to disadvantaged contexts with less economic, social, and cultural capital. ✓ Possibility of an <i>ex-post</i> evaluation of the transfers made. 	<p><i>The ability of projects to contribute to the implementation of national action plans and be in line with local, regional, and national political priorities.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Coherence with the goals of local and European political agendas, particularly with those related to migrant integration. ✓ Protocols with public administrations. ✓ Granting of public funds. ✓ Impact of good practices on the local decision-making system (public and private decision-makers’ policies; allocation of local resources). ✓ Impact on the government and conditions of particularly disadvantaged contexts.

3.1.2 Approaches and Areas of Interest

The IMMERSE project identified the most relevant outcomes in the successful integration and socio-educational inclusion of refugee and migrant children in society, which are expressed in the IMMERSE Common Conceptual Framework and, more specifically, in the Dashboard of Indicators³. The Dashboard consists of 30 indicators divided into 14 integration outcomes and 16 barriers and determinants. The integration outcomes correspond to 5 dimensions: *access to rights, language and culture, well-being, connectedness, and educational achievements*, which reflect the degree of integration of children. These outcomes led partners to consider the following areas as relevant for the identification of good practices:

Table 1. IMMERSE Dashboard – Outcomes of integration

O1. Outcomes in access to rights	Access to rights	Access to compulsory education
		Access to health care
* The outcome “Access to legal rights,” which was dropped from the final dashboard, is still interesting for the purpose of this report, therefore, it is kept in the analysis.		
O2. Outcomes in language & culture	Host language	Children's competence in host language
	Interculturalism	Children maintain their cultural identity while adopting new cultural values and intercultural competences

* The outcome “Children’s competence in their mother tongue,” which was dropped from the final dashboard, is still interesting for the purpose of this report, therefore, it is kept in the analysis.

³ <https://www.immerse-h2020.eu/selection-and-creation-of-dashboard-of-socio-educational-integration-indicators/>

O3. Outcomes in well-being	Subjective well-being	Children's life satisfaction / happiness
		Children's sense of belonging
<i>* The outcome "Children's self-esteem," which was dropped from the final dashboard, is still interesting for the purpose of this report, therefore, it is kept in the analysis.</i>		
O4. Outcomes in connectedness	Interconnectedness	Friends and peers (support)
		Friends and peers (bridges)
		Teachers
		Institutions
O5. Outcomes in educational achievements	Academic skills	Children's academic skills
	Levels and types of education attained	Children complete compulsory education
		Children remain in (formal) education beyond compulsory levels / Access to (formal) non-compulsory education
		Types & levels of (formal) non-compulsory education attended

To identify good practices, IMMERSE research partners explored inclusion initiatives carried out at local, national, or regional levels and activated in different settings within the social system:

Micro	Meso	Macro
the child and his/her family	community, services, organizations, and institutions that are in close proximity to the child in his/her daily life (schools, neighbourhood, social services, associations, etc.)	the political, economic, and social systems of a given society and the related policies

3.2 The Process

The good practices collection followed a methodology designed around six key steps. Partners were actively involved in setting the framework and searching, analysing, evaluating, and reporting proved good practices of socio-educational inclusion of migrant and refugee children. In this section, we will elaborate on the process phases.

1. Methodology and Template Development

Once a common theoretical framework was defined, a methodology and a timeline were shared with partners. It was important to establish a common understanding of the notion of good practice and lay the general groundwork for the identification of good practices. An ad hoc form was structured with closed- and open-ended questions in order to understand the elements corresponding to the discussed parameters.

2. Cases Candidature

The research teams at the national level nominated – on a monthly basis – one relevant practice that they considered of interest for a total of 10 good practices per partner. Partners identified these cases based on the criteria approved in the methodology and, with the contribution of project representatives in some instances, described them in the ad hoc form, reporting basic information concerning the objectives, targets, activities, actors involved, methods, and results, etc. Official documents and project materials were also enclosed to enrich the available information. The final database consists of 60 good practices at the local, national and European levels.

3. Comparative Analysis

Once the 60 good practices were mapped and the database was completed with all the information, a comparative analysis was conducted to obtain a comprehensive overview of the characteristics of the selected good practices and share the insight gained from these different initiatives. We investigated the type of action, target, level of implementation, as well as correspondence to the identification parameters. We further discussed some cross-cutting features among projects and actions that appear to be linked to the successful achievement of the pursued objectives and that can inspire to operationalize lessons learned.

4. Detection of In-Depth Case Studies and Interview Strategy Development

Beyond the comparative analysis of 60 good practices, the data collection phase allowed the selection of a restricted number of inspiring initiatives to be studied in depth through a qualitative interview with the project representative/manager and possibly an additional relevant actor, stakeholder, or beneficiary.

With reference to the information collected and considering the IMMERSE theoretical framework, 12 initiatives (2 practices per partner) were identified for the in-depth analysis. The cases were selected based on their compliance with the good practice parameters (efficacy, efficiency, reproducibility and transferability, political relevance), balanced with their heterogeneity with respect to the dashboard outcomes: all else being equal, cases covering different fields of intervention were selected. Following this first sampling, the projects were evaluated according to the availability of comprehensive documentation and their innovative approaches to the socio-educational inclusion of migrant and refugee children.

For the in-depth case studies, each partner was required to collect and share primary data. Interview guidelines were developed to provide partners with all the necessary indications for arranging and conducting an interview. The process of developing the template for interviewing the case study providers was based on the necessity to provide a common structure to facilitate effective communication and, at the same time, allow space for the specificity of the practices to be raised.

5. Interviews

The objective of the interview was twofold: firstly, the aim was to collect more specific and holistic information about the initiative, starting from any missing or incomplete information resulting from the first phase of the case's candidature. Secondly, the goal was to highlight strengths and elements of success that classify the project as a good practice. The correspondence of the project to the identification requirements for a good practice was indeed examined more profoundly, and a story of success was collected to highlight the positive impact of the project in terms of migrant and refugee children's socio-educational inclusion.

The interviewing process took quite a time and was labour-intensive, but it represented a networking occasion and a golden opportunity to exchange knowledge. The outcome is a database of 12 rich and informative good practices, filled with interesting information, human voices, and successful stories.

6. Report Drafting and Dissemination

The results from the analysis of the 60 good practices, as well as the information collected from the 12 in-depth case-studies' interviews, are published in this report. The first draft was shared with the technical committee, and the inputs received from the partners were crucial to finalizing the work. The report has been uploaded on the EC platform and will be disseminated at the national and EU level through advocacy, networking, and dissemination initiatives.

Box 1. Challenges to the Data Collection Process

The collection of good practices was a stimulating activity. In line with IMMERSE's methodology of co-creation and agents' empowerment, the whole process of good practices collection incentivized the building of networks and synergies among experts and stakeholders, who were active in researching examples and getting in touch with project initiators to collect and share information. However, the whole process encountered some challenging issues. Firstly, the design of effective good practice collection tools needed to be structured in such a way as to balance standardization and flexibility. Templates offered a defined structure enriched by more options and additional spaces for integrating comments in order, on the one hand, to meet the requirements of comparative analysis needs while, on the other hand, highlighting project specificities. Secondly, some projects, especially initiatives that were locally and nationally implemented, provided information and materials only in the country's language. To overcome this linguistic barrier, IMMERSE partners translated project descriptions into English. Thirdly, partners found gaps in data research. Information related to the identification requirements for a good practice was indeed not always available or easily accessible. Especially, information about evaluation, transferability, and political relevance was not always straightforwardly publicised or discussed in the project materials. In some cases, direct contact with project representatives and the interviewing process contributed to overcoming these limits. Additionally, in carrying out interviews, we had to deal with the unavailability of project representatives due to the temporal gap between the end of the project and the IMMERSE interview. Last but not least, the COVID-19 emergency impacted the work of both the consortium and the case studies' providers, delaying the research activities in some instances or limiting the supply of data.

4 Comparative Analysis

From September 2020 to June 2021, the IMMERSE research partners collected 60 good practices whose features were reported in a database to facilitate comparative analysis. The aim of this study is to offer a comprehensive and informative (though non-exhaustive) overview of noteworthy initiatives implemented at the local, national, and European levels in the field of socio-educational inclusion of children with a migratory background. Beyond depicting the areas of action, the typology of the target, as well as the level of implementation, we investigated projects' cross-cutting features with reference to the quality criteria used to identify a good practice. This analysis thus provides a limited but useful examination of approaches, experiences, and initiatives, whose characteristics can be consulted for inspiration, as well as for discussion and reflection about the recent European spectrum of projects aimed at the socio-educational inclusion of migrant children. The analysis provides a wealth of contextualised data related to the 60 case studies that were taken into account for this analysis. However, despite the review process, there are differences in consistency, quantity, and level of detail between the collected practices. Moreover, practices have been developed in different timeframes previous to the data collection process, while some of them are still ongoing.

Annex 1 shows all the case studies specified by title and provides useful links to learn more about the initiatives.

4.1 Which Good Practices?

4.1.1 Aims and activities

The 60 good practices offer a wide range of diverse activities designed to reach the short and long-term inclusion goals. In 78% of the cases, initiatives implement multiple activities according to the assumption that the socio-educational inclusion of children with a migratory background is interpreted from and aimed at different perspectives and processes. The prevalence of projects characterized by a multiplicity and simultaneity of interventions suggests a widespread attempt to adopt an approach based on the multidimensional undertaking of inclusion.

Surely, the language is considered a key tool of integration: 25 out of 60 projects propose language classes for the acquisition of both mother tongue and host country language skills. Similarly, language is used as a fundamental element in educative projects, as in the case of “L’AltRoparlante” project, which promotes a “translanguaging turn” to include all students’ individual and collective linguistic repertoires in the curricular educational activities in six Italian schools, in the light of a multilingual and intercultural learning approach.

The process of socio-educational inclusion is further pursued through extracurricular activities, with 55% of the projects providing homework support, leisure and free-time activities such as sport, music, art, and dance classes. A good example is “In Crescendo” a musical educational project implemented in an urban area of Valladolid (Spain), where students take part in instrument construction workshops and join the orchestra with which they perform live in different places.

Almost 1 out of 3 projects offers vocational training, including internships, youth work experiences, and professional courses for teachers and school staff. Mentoring and tutoring enrich the offering. The project “Enable-Tamkin,” for instance, developed a training concept and a training tool for Arabic-speaking teachers,

educators, and volunteers to support newly immigrated children with innovative pedagogical methods, such as self-organised learning.

Good practices further include a wealth of support activities such as legal and school counselling, psychological support, family interventions, and actions to foster parents’ participation (28.3%).

There are then a few but great examples of case studies that focus on the role of schools in the process of inclusion, proposing innovative educational and management models (20%). Meaningful examples are the SEDIN project which promotes Montessori and Creative Learning methods, the Multitasking Cooperative Classrooms project that provides an innovative classroom reorganisation, and the In.Media.Res project which adopts a community of practice approach.

Interestingly, a good number of projects implement research activities aimed at developing toolkits, handbooks, platforms (15%), as well as training concepts and thematic courses (8.3%). Additionally, some case studies (36.7%) aim to create networks, exchange good practices of inclusion, and lead advocacy initiatives and dissemination events to raise awareness and formulate policy recommendations addressed to the educational and policy sectors, which are relevant to promoting and reaching inclusion.

Graph 1. Projects’ activities designed to reach socio-educational inclusion goals (n. out of 60).

4.1.2 Targets

IMMERSE project investigates the socio-educational integration of the whole general population of children with a migrant background, which includes specific sub-groups and involves different stakeholders in the process. The good practices collected show that there is a growing commitment to take action and initiate programmes with a multi-stakeholder approach. Indeed, 95% of projects address multiple targets.

The data in *Graph 2* show that 2 out of 3 projects are devoted to first and/or second-generation migrant children (70%). Moreover, many projects focus on specific children's groups, such as newly arrived migrant children (73.3%), unaccompanied and separated children (56.7%), and refugee and asylum-seeking children (60%).

Meaningfully, almost half of the initiatives are also addressed to migrant families (53.3%), principals and teachers (56.7%), and educators and social workers (45%), who represent crucial actors in children’s educational and social development. Finally, policy makers and educational authorities benefit from 40% of the projects, while a minority of initiatives are also addressed to “other” targets (28.3%), such as children without a migratory background, young adults, academics and researchers, associations, and the community as a whole.

Graph 2. Target groups of the 60 good practices (n. out of 60).

4.1.3 Level of implementation

IMMERSE partners put a large emphasis on identifying initiatives that could be labelled as “good” practices. Considering that a project, process, or result cannot be said to be “good” *tout court* but only relative to a specific context of reference and a specific need, as shown in the pie chart below, IMMERSE research partners collected a database of 25 local scale (41%) and 19 nation-wide (32%) successful projects, which better reflect this approach. Among this selection, there are small-scale initiatives, projects suited to fit the peculiarity of a given context, or programs grounded on a community-based approach.

As shown in the pie chart, the remaining practices are implemented at the European/international level (27%). Large-scale projects represent golden opportunities for transnational cooperation, knowledge transfer, and experiences exchange. The scale of these cross-border cooperation projects provides access to a transnational pool of resources and social capital and increases the transferability of project results. Beyond building

bridges, they face the challenge of balancing the standardisation required by targeting similar groups and cross-border issues and the flexibility needed to address the specificities of certain situations.

Graph 3. Level of implementation of the 60 good practices (n. out of 60 and %).

4.2 Key Findings

In accordance with the adopted methodology and the identification requirements for a good practice mentioned in section 2, IMMERSE partners collected information regarding the 60 case studies and investigated a number of quality criteria in order to provide interesting insights about the cross-cutting features of the good practices. Specifically, the following elements were analysed:

- Integration outcomes
- Monitoring & Evaluation
- Expertise and professionalism
- Networks and partnerships
- Communication and dissemination
- Reproducibility and transferability
- Funds and resources

These key features are fundamental measurable indicators of *efficacy*, *efficiency*, *reproducibility & transferability*, and *political relevance*. Nevertheless, each indicator should also be understood as a generative process capable of activating certain processes during its own development. More specifically, these cross-sectional outputs contribute to increasing the social capital and foster the empowerment of all stakeholders and targets involved. In other words, the analysed elements have the potential to generate positive impacts, which are more difficult to assess but are key to explaining the success of socially innovative projects. This suggestion is linked to the consideration of stakeholders or users as social agents with an active role in shaping innovation processes.

Keeping this approach in mind, the following paragraphs summarise the key findings of the elements of success in terms of social innovation for migrant children's inclusion in Europe and serve as much stimulating food for thought.

4.2.1 Integration Outcomes

A project is successful if it is able to meet the planned goals, i.e., to foster and improve the socio-educational integration of the target groups. In this, efficacy is classically intended as a result-related feature, but, as previously explained, an initiative has the potential to additionally generate virtuous processes during its own development, emphasizing and enhancing social innovation. In this sense, efficacy should be assessed considering the project's success in both reaching the established outcomes and activating certain positive processes.

Some of the available evaluation reports and studies show interesting results in both quantitative and qualitative terms. For instance, the Tomillo Foundation's project "Integral attention to children," guaranteed school support to 1,735 children and adolescents: 68% of them improved their academic competencies, and 78% of them their socioemotional competencies. Similarly, the Barça Foundation FutbolNet program tangibly improved the life skills, self-esteem, and self-confidence of young people, as well as helping them to better express their thoughts and feelings.

Not only have the project goals been fulfilled, but in many cases, positive side- and domino effects have also been recorded. For example, the SIRIUS project secured a commitment to migrant and refugee pupils as part of a broader agenda on inclusive education since its findings are used by several international organizations, national governments, and the EC to promote concrete policy changes, write papers, and provide recommendations on education for migrants.

In terms of integration outcomes, it is also interesting to analyse the correspondence of the practices' purposes and results to the outcomes identified in the IMMERSE dashboard of indicators, which depicts a multidimensional definition of integration, whilst also being capable of capturing the indirect and secondary benefits. This is evident when considering the association of the studied good practices, manifestly related to minor migrants' education, to the 5 dimensions of integration: as shown in the below bar chart. However, outcomes in *educational achievements* and in *language & culture* score high, it is worth noticing that outcomes in *connectedness* and *well-being* are equally important. These aspects are not always straightforwardly declared among the project objectives; however, implementers and IMMERSE partners recognized the multidimensional contribution of the initiatives to the more complex process of socio-educational inclusion.

Graph 4. Correspondence of projects' goals to the IMMERSE five dimensions of integration outcome (n.).

Considering the apparent focus on education, half of the analysed case studies aim to guarantee migrant and refugee children's access to compulsory education. Almost 80% of the projects pursue an improvement in children's academic skills, and around 65% attempt to guarantee the completion of compulsory education, followed by nearly 60% aimed at children's access to (formal) non-compulsory education.

The significant share of language classes among the declared activities, as well as the relevance of language as an integration tool, explain the fact that 7 out of 10 projects aspire to boost children's perceived competence in the language of the host country. Considering also that integration processes must not lead to assimilation, it is crucial to highlight that a significant majority of initiatives attempt to ensure that children maintain their cultural identity while adopting new cultural values and intercultural competences. Interestingly, the indicator "Children's competence in their mother tongue," which was dropped from the final dashboard, shows that 1 out of 4 projects pursue the improvement of the linguistic repertoire of migrant and refugee children.

The host society is indeed a key factor in a successful integration process. The educational dimension cannot be detached from the social dimension since schools, and other educational environments are social hubs where migrant and refugee children are in contact with friends, peers, and teachers and develop confidence and trust in institutions. Coherently, around 60% of the case studies aim at improving children's integration by working on the relationships with friends and peers (both support and bridges), and almost 70% focus on the relationships with teachers and the confidence in institutions (e.g., schools, police, hospitals). In connection to these results, it is worth noting the fact that a meaningful 90% of the projects pursue the accomplishment of children's sense of belonging, and approximately 85% aim at children's life satisfaction and happiness. The indicator related to self-esteem (not included in the final dashboard) confirms this trend with 53 out of 60 good practices pursuing this integration goal. Interestingly, the latter integration outcomes show that the projects submitted during our data collection process are largely oriented towards intercepting and intervening on issues that traditional integration processes' indicators have more difficulty in grasping and measuring but which the civil society actors intercept as key elements and needs for successful integration, such as forms of belonging, identity, and happiness.

Considering migrant children's access to legal status, 1 out of 6 projects pursue this outcome. This is probably due to the fact that the selected good practices are mostly and strongly focused on inclusive education.

Finally, what emerges from the available data is that each project is able to match and satisfy various outcomes. This proves that the candidate practices are characterized by an **extreme multidimensionality** that mirrors the complexity of socio-educational integration processes, as depicted in the IMMERSE dashboard of indicators and well-represented in the graph below.

Graph 5. Correspondence of the projects' outcomes to IMMERSE integration outcomes (n. out of 60).

4.2.2 Monitoring & Evaluation

The purpose of monitoring and evaluation (M&E) is to systematically track implementation and measure the effectiveness of the project activities through quantitative and qualitative research processes. M&E is essential to determine when an initiative is on track or when changes may be needed. The collected data allow informed decisions to be made and guide strategic planning to review activities and allocate resources in better ways, thus improving the overall project performance, sustainability, and quality.

Out of the 60 good practices analysed, 70% have conducted or will conduct an evaluation that leads to the drafting of internal or external reports, research papers, articles, and other materials. 30 out of these 42 projects have publicised their evaluation reports, resulting in greater transparency and accountability, but there is still a relevant percentage (around 30%) of projects that do not make their evaluation reports available, thus limiting the dissemination of initiatives. In fact, these publications further favour the transfer of

knowledge and good practices, which can be more easily replicated. They also provide a more robust basis for formulating recommendations and influencing policy.

Evaluation is critical in determining the extent to which an initiative can be judged as successful. A good example is the project “SIRIUS,” which is recognised as a model of good governance⁴ for migrant education, with its recommendations for reform cited by major national and international education actors, such as the UNESCO 2019 Global Education Monitoring Report⁵.

When it comes to long-term projects, periodic monitoring and comparison are useful to evaluate the outcomes properly. In the specific case of the Rohingya Resettlement project in Carlow, Ireland, a ten-year evaluation report has been published to recount the process, approach, and lessons learnt through the programme and its associated initiatives.

The process of M&E may be conducted internally or by an external authority. In some cases, such as the “HE.ST.I.A.” project, progress and satisfaction were assessed through online questionnaires directly administered and analysed by the partners. In contrast, the “Barça Foundation FutbolNet program” relied on external evaluators to showcase the project’s efforts and highlight the wide-ranging positive impacts.

Moreover, M&E may be carried out at different levels, involving various participants and stakeholders. For instance, the “Prolema” project conducted surveys and interviews over the years with the participants, the volunteers, and the pupils, in order to obtain a comparison from different perspectives and across different editions.

In only 5 case studies, an official evaluation has not been carried out, while for 13, there is no available information regarding the existence of evaluation reports. In most cases, these are local-scale context-specific projects, and contacts are provided to get more information.

4.2.3 Expertise and Professionalism

Involving professionals with experience and expertise is crucial for the successful outcome of projects aimed at the socio-educational inclusion of children with a migratory background. Moreover, good practices improve the collaboration between professionals, facilitating the creation of networks and the formation of a multi- and interdisciplinary community that provides assistance, support, and guidance to the multi-faceted process of inclusion. The engagement of professionals from different disciplines indeed ensures a high-level and qualified intervention.

Considering the focus of IMMERSE and the scope of this collection of good practices, professional staff in the field of education is predominantly present in the projects’ database, with 93.3% of the projects involving educators and/or teachers. Apart from educational practitioners, professionals from different areas of expertise are frequently involved, e.g., cultural mediators, psychologists, legal experts, and academics/researchers. More specifically, half of the projects employ cultural mediators, and around 1 out of 4 projects provide collaboration with a psychologist. Legal experts work on fewer cases, while academic practitioners are involved in 30 out of 60 projects. Youth and social workers, job experts, health professionals, sport coaches, artists, and public operators are among the other practitioners cited in the analysed initiatives.

⁴ <https://www.sirius-migrationeducation.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Report-on-Evaluation-of-SIRIUS-Key-achievements-1.pdf>

⁵ UNESCO, 2018. *Global Education Monitoring Report 2019: Migration, Displacement and Education – Building Bridges, not Walls*. Paris, UNESCO.

The engagement of qualified experts is even more significant when professionals from different disciplines work jointly. It is noteworthy that the cases involving just one professional figure are quite rare (8.3%). In contrast, almost 70% of the initiatives involve two to four categories of practitioners, and more than 23% engage over 5 different professional figures.

There are many interesting examples in the database of initiatives that involve a relevant number of professional roles. For instance, the In.Media.Res project conceives intercultural mediation as a multi-stakeholder process to be achieved through the creation of a community of practice. The implementation phase thus requires the engagement of a group of practitioners from different areas of expertise – education, intercultural mediation, ethnopsychology, cultural anthropology, and migration law – able to intercept the multiple aspects and fields of inclusion processes.

4.2.4 Networks and Partnerships

Integration is a multi-level and multi-dimensional process. Hence, it needs a multi-stakeholder approach to be effective and sustainable. Collaboration with a variety of actors is an important parameter in assessing the quality and success of a project. All 60 identified initiatives have developed a partnership and/or joined a diversified network of stakeholders, ranging from governmental and local authorities to NGOs, school communities, universities, and research centres. In some instances, these projects can rely on a longstanding and solid network of stakeholders, while in other cases the initiative gives rise to new fruitful collaborations.

Analysing the database of initiatives, public authorities are involved in 75% of the cases, as depicted in *Graph 6*. Given the local scale of most analysed initiatives, local authorities are a more mentioned stakeholder than national and supranational entities. Networking and/or partnerships created with political or administrative authorities is an indicator of the political relevance of the initiative and its coherence with the goals of local and European political agendas, particularly those related to migrant integration. NGOs and other third sector and civil society organizations collaborate closely as project partners or supporters in almost 82% of the initiatives. The focus of the wide range of projects on the socio-educational inclusion of children with a migratory background also reveals the large contribution of stakeholders within the education sector, especially schools and student/parents associations, which collaborate in 44 and 26 out of 60 cases, respectively. Approximately 6 out of 10 projects develop a collaboration network, including universities and/or research centres, which often represent a source of scientific information and a channel for knowledge-transfer. Finally, in some cases, enterprises, foundations, employment, and training agencies are mentioned as stakeholders.

Another general trend that we can observe from our database is that the multi-stakeholder approach is a common feature. It is meaningful that most projects involve different types of actors – among those mentioned above, which contribute with their expertise and experiences of inclusion to the project goals, providing their own specific perspective. As shown in the chart below, in only 15 cases, networks are relatively modest with one or two typologies of stakeholders involved, whereas in 45 out of 60 initiatives, more than 3 and up to 7 different typologies of actors are mentioned.

The Interreg project “SIREE” aims to facilitate refugees’ social and economic integration by increasing the engagement of refugees in the education process and improving their economic independence through self-employment. Nine partners lead the initiative, including universities, research centres, municipalities, NGOs, and an open knowledge centre. Moreover, the government, schools, and student/parents’ associations collaborate for a successful outcome. Similarly, the “RESTORE” project, aimed at developing a restorative

model for schools all over Europe, is grounded on the partnership of 7 diverse actors and establishes an innovative collaboration between training organisations, schools, local authorities, and a research centre.

Generally speaking, the engagement of multiple and diverse stakeholders and their collaboration through common integrated efforts allows for the implementation of effective actions geared at achieving a comprehensive and holistic socio-educational inclusion of migrant and refugee children.

Graph 6. Stakeholders of the 60 good practices (n. out of 60).

4.2.5 Communication and Dissemination

An important factor in determining the quality of a project in terms of sustainability, reproducibility, and knowledge-sharing is communication. According to their objectives and scope, good practices shall adopt an efficient and effective communication and dissemination strategy to raise awareness about the societal challenges affecting a community and the project activities implemented to overcome them. Furthermore, the external communication of the actions could be of inspiration for other initiatives, providing a successful example of socio-educational inclusion or useful advice on the topic to favour reproducibility and transferability.

The IMMERSE database shows that all 60 case studies have utilised communication tools to disseminate information, tools, and results. The completeness, accuracy, and effectiveness of the communication strategy, however, varies across projects, with the sharing of more or less detailed descriptions, generic or specific information, translated documents, and full or partial deliverables.

Each project develops ad-hoc deliverables to best suit its aims and target: from traditional handouts and newsletters to project reports and presentations, manuals and books, toolkits and training materials, or more scientific publications such as articles and research papers, videos, posts, and apps. A good example is the project “Refugee Resettlement: Addressing Educational Needs of Newly Arrived Syrian and Iraqi Students in Ireland,” which developed a toolkit based on the learning and range of interventions emanating from the project and covering different aspects of the resettlement and integration process, such as pre-arrival, planning, dealing with finances, health and wellbeing, and support for women, children and young people. Likewise, the “Rucksack Schule - School Backpack” initiative designed teaching and training materials to use both in the classroom and at school to promote multilingualism and intercultural education. Videos and events are key deliverables of the project “ICAM,” while the project “Case Management Tool for Non-formal Education in Youth Work” focuses on the production of the digital app StreetSmart.

Deliverables are disseminated through a wealth of channels: websites, social networks, events, emails, etc. Many projects, especially medium and large-scale projects, develop an ad-hoc website dedicated to the

project (e.g., “Enable-tamkin” project), while in other cases, initiatives are promoted via an EU portal or a specific page on a sponsoring partner’s website (e.g., “HESTIA” project). Facebook, Instagram, and emails are common communication channels that facilitate updating the project’s activities. For instance, the “Groep Intro” project uses social media and newsletters to reach the public. Dissemination is also pursued through in-person or virtual meetings, conferences, and other dissemination events.

4.2.6 Reproducibility and Transferability

Although a project is designed to suit a specific context of reference and respond to a specific need, the notion of *good practice* commonly indicates a novel and creative initiative that can also be subject to a mainstreaming process and be transposed – completely or partially – to other contexts. In this framework, **reproducibility** refers specifically to the interventions’ potential to be replicated in similar contexts, while **transferability** means the capacity of a practice to be adapted to and replicated in different contexts. This potential ensures the sustainability of the project activities and outcomes. However, the changing societal context over time and across territories needs to be taken into consideration.

Based on the limited information available, 30% of the analysed projects have been replicated and scaled up in other contexts as foreseen in the project planning, as in the case of “Cork Migrant Centre Youth Group Support,” which has been replicated in 6 Direct Provision Centres according to the project activities. This is a first demonstration that the good practice is flexible and has the potential to be replicated in varying situations. In more than 20% of the cases, a concrete replication of the initiatives to similar and/or different contexts has also been registered. This is coherent with many projects explicitly mentioning replicability among their main goals. For instance, the research project “FAMILIA” – aimed at understanding the social unrests of migrant children and families derived from transnational migration – has been designed with sustainability and reproducibility in mind. Every step of the research has been made clear and shareable, the effectiveness and reproducibility of each action have been evaluated, and suggestions for best practices in each area have been provided to favour replicability.

There are also many cases, around 77%, where replicability and upscaling are not straightforward objectives. Nevertheless, these practices – or some of their elements – can be hypothetically and potentially extended to similar and/or different contexts thanks to the availability of deliverables, tools, project information, and contact details. Obviously, materials in a foreign language and limited access to information can limit the reproducibility and especially the transferability of the initiative. A compelling example is the case study “In crescendo.” Although there are no reproducibility documents, the project has been replicated in six educational centres, located in other areas of Spain with different socio-demographic and cultural characteristics, and it continues to have a positive impact on the student body. Similarly, the “Su.Per.” project provides a complete overview and a detailed description of the research methodology in a published volume in order to make the research idea highly reproducible in other contexts and with other groups.

The practices mentioned are easily transferable to benefit the wider goal of socio-educational integration of migrant and refugee children. The present report aims to provide real examples and know-how from which we can learn and work towards new and successful ways of inclusion. With adequate investments, the analysed cases can be replicated and scaled up in similar/different contexts with small changes to the specific conditions of those new situations.

4.2.7 Funds and Resources

Financial support is a catalyst for the development and sustainability of high-quality integration initiatives. Promoting and incentivizing positive and effective actions aimed at the socio-educational inclusion of migrant children is indeed necessary to attract and allocate adequate funds.

The IMMERSE database of initiatives offers an overview of the main funding sources of the selected projects, as shown in *Graph 7*. Considering the scope of action and the accessible funding opportunities, almost half of the projects are funded by the European Union (45%) – especially through the Erasmus+ programme and the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund –, and a meaningful number receive financial support by a governmental institution, including local, regional, and national authorities (38.3%). The allocation of such funds reflects the political attention placed on integration processes, which are perceived as a societal challenge and opportunity included in the most recent national and European political agendas. In addition, 20 out of 60 projects are financed or co-funded by foundations, whereas 27 case studies use other sources, such as own resources, private funds, business and bank donations, and contributions from international organizations.

This data reflects a funding scheme in which half of the initiatives include two or more funding sources to cover the overall expenditure, considering that multiple funding mechanisms provide funds up to a given percentage.

Graph 7. Funding sources of the 60 good practices (n. out of 60).

Graph 8. Number of funding sources of the 60 good practices (n. out of 60 and %).

5 Highlighted Cases

Out of all 60 case studies, 12 good practices show interesting potential for up-scaling and offer a unique perspective and learning opportunity for practitioners and policy makers. Favouring a balanced representation of each partner's proposals, these cases were firstly selected considering their compliance with the good practice parameters, balanced with their heterogeneity with respect to the Dashboard outcomes. Secondly, the projects were evaluated according to their innovative approaches to the socio-educational inclusion of migrant and refugee children and the availability of complete information.

Generally speaking, these good practices show a variety of inspiring initiatives, both in formal and non-formal socio-educational contexts and provide further ideas on how to address a specific topic or target in the process of migrant and refugee children's socio-educational inclusion. Therefore, they represent a golden opportunity for schools, operators, decision-makers, and the wider public to learn more about positive practices and be inspired to act.

5.1 Embracing Diversity Nurturing Integration Project (EDNIP)

EDNIP is a research and intervention project that originated in a network of school principals in Limerick, OSCAILT, which is the Irish word for “open/opening.” Formed in 2009, OSCAILT was initially made up of 16 school principals who met periodically to discuss issues and share concerns. At one of their meetings in 2017, the increasing diversity of student populations and the growing awareness of the need to support migrant integration across several local organisations led to the creation of EDNIP. EDNIP is a partnership project between Mary Immaculate College of Education, five schools, the Department of Education, Tusla Educational Support Services, Limerick City and County Council, Limerick and Clare Education and Training Board, and Limerick Education Centre.

The EDNIP project aims at promoting integration through the sharing of experiences of five participating schools in supporting migrant families. Its goals are aligned with the National Council for Curriculum and Assessment’s (NCCA) draft of the Primary Curriculum Framework, and the challenges identified regarding diversity and interculturalism in schools speak directly to the national policy direction for inclusion.

EDNIP promotes integration through **modelling effective inclusive, and transparent governance practices based on a very clear management scheme**. The project encompasses several levels of governance – the Project Management Committee (PMC), which oversees the project, is made up of the principals as well as state educational, child support, and welfare representatives operating locally; and the School Integration Committees (SIC), comprised of principals, school staff, parents, a public health nurse, a pre-school manager and pupils, that directs project activities in each school. Their actual make up differs depending on the context, the network, and the key issues of concern pertaining to each specific school. Additionally, the principals, represented at each of these levels, engage in networking with OSCAILT and with the School Boards of Management through regular reporting on the initiatives. Overall, this governance structure provides **clear communication lines**.

Key actions of the EDNIP project consist in **listening to and learning from school staff, parents, and children; promoting capacity building for school staff; nurturing parents and community engagement and skill development; and modelling effective interagency**. The schools promote intercultural education, family support, STEAM, and drama activities. EDNIP also organises and delivers a range of CPD opportunities for existing school staff, including EPV summer programmes.

Overall, **the project views the child in the context of their family and community**, so it includes support for children inside and outside of school time, including holidays, as well as support for parents that would enable them to assist with their children’s education and integration and, in turn, their own integration. The inclusion of parents and the development of initiatives that address their needs are indeed key for a successful integration process. This contributes to building strong relationships in safe environments which are beneficial to children and their parents and which enhance mutual understanding across school and community, as happened with the parent and toddler group set up in the DEIS infant school. This holistic view of the child, extending beyond school activities and community, is central to the success of the project and a meaningful integration path.

*“(…) it’s about working with teachers. It’s working on school management. It’s working with parents. It’s working with children. It’s doing all of that in school after the school holiday time” -
Representative of EDNIP Project*

Researching, developing, and purchasing resources was a large element of the EDNIP project. This stressed the fact that resourcing schools is imperative, especially in terms of the provision of easily accessible materials, representative of the diversity of children.

“So there is a template there that can be scaled up [...] it proves that schools are a site for integration” - Representative of EDNIP Project

The project has a high potential to be replicated. EDNIP partners adopted an **effective communication strategy**, distributing information through articles and conferences. However, the key to its success and the success of any replication of the project is that schools self-select and make decisions on what interventions are best suited to their contexts as well as the make-up of their school integration committees. Additionally, the **identification of champions** within schools is essential to drive the project activities and ensure the holistic engagement of children and their families. There is a case to be made for a position of responsibility within schools for integration, encompassing out-of-school activities.

EDNIP ran from 2017 to 2019. A reduced version ran in 2020/2021 and will continue till 2023.

Highlight

Building trust emerged as a very important element, especially with parents of children who might be experiencing isolation and find it difficult to understand practices and procedures. The role of the parent/toddler group was extremely important: parents and children found a safe place. The forum provided a space where information on vaccinations and public health practices could be explained and clarified. It also provided a space where staff and parents could build solid relationships. This became very important as COVID restrictions were implemented, leading to children and families isolating in their homes. Through the relationships of trust that were built and a permanent communication channel, it was possible to identify and address the needs of families.

Useful links and materials

Higgins, A., Lyne, A., Power, S., and Murphy, M. (2021). *Embracing Diversity Nurturing Integration Project (EDNIP): sharing the story, evolution, model and outcomes of a research and intervention project in five DEIS Band 1 primary schools in Limerick City 2017-2019*. Available at: <https://www.mic.ul.ie/sites/default/files/uploads/140/EDNIP%202020%20Full%20Report.pdf>

Addressing Issues of Social Exclusion in Moyross and Other areas of disadvantage in Limerick. Report to the Cabinet Committee on Social Inclusion. Available at: <http://www.limerickregeneration.org/MoyrossReptApr07.pdf>

INTO Newsletter *Touch*. See article “If we were all the same you wouldn’t know who you are” <https://intouch.into.ie/html5/reader/production/default.aspx?pubname=&pubid=b5e9d7cd-6832-4cbd-8c50-96ba8cc9ab12>

5.2 FRIDA Project - Training for the prevention and detection of racism and xenophobia in the classroom⁶

The FRIDA project was conducted by the OBERAXE, the Spanish Observatory on Racism and Xenophobia, which belongs to the General Directorate of Inclusion and Humanitarian Attention of the Secretary of State for Migration. The project has its origin in the call of the European Commission's Progress Program 2013 for the Employment and Social Solidarity and received additional funds from the Spanish government and the Autonomous Communities. The entire project was **framed within the national agenda for the inclusion of migrants** and complied with state provisions for the elimination of racial discrimination, xenophobia, and other related forms of intolerance in education. It was implemented in four Autonomous Communities from November 2014 to October 2015, and Awareness Days were held in the following years.

The FRIDA project is implemented in **schools** as this educational space is considered **a key spot for youth and children, a safe space where they develop their identities**

and their intercultural competences and learn to value diversity from an enrichment perspective. The project's general aim is to impart training for the **prevention and detection of racism, xenophobia, and other related forms of intolerance in the classroom**, reinforcing the positive image of migrants' integration and ethnic minorities in the field of education. The project seeks to sensitize and provide tools to teachers and educational managers to prevent, identify and deal with such incidents.

To this end, experts on racism and xenophobia in schools developed a **handbook**, which is publicly available on the OBERAXE website, not only in Spanish but also with a summary of their proposal in English and other two co-official languages in Spain – Galician and Basque. The support manual describes the reasons for the existence of xenophobia, racism, and other forms of intolerance; offers a diagnosis of the situation of migrant and minority communities and the regulatory framework; and lists the strategies for prevention and awareness in educational centres, as well as the effects that these incidents have and the best way to deal with them. The methodology used is the narrative synthesis, enriched by a review of pre-existing literature.

The handbook was disseminated through **awareness campaigns**, where stakeholders, especially the educational leaders of all Autonomous Communities in Spain, were engaged. In the years after the project's formal conclusion, due to the ongoing demand, project leaders have continued to organize seminars throughout Spain, using their own resources and those of the Autonomous Communities, always in collaboration with the Ministry of Education. The seminars are tailor-made for each Community, and good practices are disseminated, which, as a result, are adopted by the Communities or city councils themselves. In this way, the seminars also have become a platform for linking different stakeholders with the same objectives in different regions and contexts.

In addition to the widespread dissemination within Spain, UNESCO requested to upload the manual on its website, and the Spanish Cooperation Agency (AECID) requested seminars in Latin America with participants from the entire region.

“We had a meeting with all the education representatives of the Autonomous Communities, we asked them what their needs were in relation to the issue of preventing racism and xenophobia (...) they said they needed training” - Karoline Fernández de la Hoz Zeitler, Director of OBERAXE

⁶ Original title: Proyecto FRIDA: “Formación para la prevención y detección del racismo, la xenofobia y otras formas de intolerancia en las aulas”.

Overall, the handbook and the dissemination process have been evaluated as a great success. This is confirmed by the expression of interest received by many Autonomous Communities, as well as by the external evaluation conducted in 2017, which concludes that the FRIDA project had a good impact on the educational administrations in terms of participation of educators in conferences and the dissemination of project materials. The project was welcomed by and raised **engagement from different educational administrations**, a fact that is attested by the promotion of teacher training in the prevention of racism, xenophobia, and other forms of intolerance throughout a number of Communities, such as Castilla y León or Castilla-La Mancha. It is also reflected in the Valencian Community, where the PREVI registration system now includes information on the motivation of the incidents that are raised. Further, it is reflected in the inclusion of a section on the prevention and treatment of intolerance in the Ministry of Education and Professional Training's Coexistence Plan.

The synergies that have occurred between society and the various administrations are the basis for future actions and contribute to examining in depth the new methods of educational integration illustrated by the project.

Highlight

In the Valencian Community, about 2000 people from educational centres throughout the region play the role of "coexistence coordinator." The Community of Valencia was interested in taking advantage of the FRIDA project's seminar organized to disseminate the manual as a training for these coordinators. The seminar was held at the *Palau de las Arts* with about 1000 attendees. The experts who had designed the manual gave a presentation on the manual itself as well as other positive experiences seen throughout the region, including the PREVI project. PREVI is a system implemented in Valencia for registering incidents and aggressions in real-time, where people can declare the incident they were victims of, or that they witnessed. The Education Department then evaluates the severity of the event and contacts them to solve it. One variable that was previously not included in the declaration was the motivation for the incident. After the FRIDA seminars, a decision was made to include the motivation in order to detect incidents related to racism and xenophobia and to be able to make an intervention that would be more suitable to the situation.

Useful Links and Materials

<https://www.inclusion.gob.es/oberaxe/es/ejes/educacion/frida/index.htm>

5.3 ICAM Network

The acronym CAM (Children Affected by Migration) is used when referring to children who are refugees, asylum seekers, economic or social migrants, or those left behind by family moving to another country.

At the heart of the ICAM project is the concept of ‘*convivencia*’ – a Spanish word meaning ‘living together in harmony’ and the knowledge that children’s well-being can be influenced by the school climate. The purpose of the ICAM project is to increase inclusion and improve the learning capacity of children affected by migration by enhancing the **climate of *convivencia* in schools and at home**, by raising awareness about children’s rights and the law protecting them, and by providing additional support in school and in the family for their Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) and general wellbeing.

To reach this goal, the project provides for the **professional development of school leaders, who will increase the capacity of schools to maintain a safe and secure learning environment and enhance Social and Emotional Learning**. ICAM national facilitators provide useful tools and train school leaders to adopt a whole-school approach to the inclusion of these children based on creating a climate of *convivencia*. They essentially provide leadership training to school leaders, stimulating a cascade effect within the school system. The programme has 12 practical areas, including parents’ and children’s engagement, and provides a training toolkit used by schools to create formal and informal curricula development. The efficacy of the training and the programme is yearly assessed by the school community through a co-created review instrument. ICAM further integrates parent/carer education to provide additional support for families and encourage ongoing SEL also in the home.

Funded by the European Commission (EACEA) with co-funding from Erasmus+, ICAM Programme first ran in 2018 for a two-year pilot that ran in 65 schools in four countries. The pilot was positively evaluated and is now running on its second iteration, the goal of which is to find **school champions to promote the programme and scale-up the project** by getting all schools in an area to adopt it. **Working with and involving stakeholders at the local level** has indeed demonstrated to be easier compared to setting up a regional framework, especially regarding the engagement of political educational authorities.

“The programme is designed to support whole-school development, but is also designed to be adopted nationally, not small-scale.” - Chris Gittins, Lead Partner,

The ICAM will be focusing the next six months on finding a way to make the programme sustainable, by having a major international organisation adopt it and take it forward. The hope is to extend ICAM’s important work beyond the end of this second cycle and place SEL and emotional well-being at the heart of the school environment.

Highlight

A main obstacle encountered by ICAM in Spain is the reluctance of schools and headmasters to change and adopt new teaching approaches within the learning environment, although the COVID situation has demonstrated the importance of a positive social and emotional foundation for learning for all children. Another major obstacle regards the political agenda at the regional level, where the implementation of novel ideas can be difficult. Although the ICAM programme is being implemented in several cities across Spain, the difficulty of engaging stakeholders directly, and the resistance to innovation, are barriers that can be seen alongside the difficulties in engaging with the political educational authority.

Useful Links and Materials

<https://www.icamproject.eu/>

<https://www.eurochild.org/uploads/2021/06/Roundtable-discussion-Chris-Gittins-The-ICAMnet-Programme.pdf>

5.4 In.Media.Res – Integration Mediation Responsibility⁷

The EU-funded project InMediaRes was implemented in the Turin province during the school year 2013-14. It was realized in a limited number of neighbourhoods, selecting schools with a meaningful share of students with a migrant background based on the idea that **the school is the fundamental environment for the integration of children and their families.**

InMediaRes aimed at overcoming the barriers to the socio-educational inclusion of newly arrived migrant minors with third-country citizenship by creating a **sustainable and replicable model of mediation intervention** available to all schools. This model is grounded on an **interdisciplinary approach that encompasses intercultural mediation, ethnopsychology, cultural anthropology, and migration law and favours the creation of a “community of practice.”** i.e., a group of professionals capable of responding comprehensively to complex issues, thanks to their expertise and through active collaboration, the creation of networks, and the sharing of good practices and knowledge.

“The fact that the teacher could share a path with educators, mediators and families was the ideal condition to guarantee a fair integration and a comprehensive care of the child” -
Roberta Valetti, Project Coordinator,
IRES Piemonte researcher

“It was a fantastic effort of teachers and mediators (...) to provide teachers with the tools to understand the difficulties of a child who migrates during his or her scholastic path”. - Sabina Tangerini, CCM – Education Representative

One of the main workstreams regarded the strict cooperation between schools and mediators in overcoming the traditional fragmented approach, and fostering **intercultural mediation as an integrated territorial service and school approach.** To this end, a group of mediators offered communication support and provided the school staff with the right tools and information to initiate adequate educational paths for migrant children, deconstruct stereotypes and misinformation, and reinforce the relational dynamic with pupils. Moreover, an activity with teachers, mediators, and NGOs representatives was organized to discover

and learn more about the scholastic paths of children in other countries and to overcome the school staff’s lack of awareness about the **differences in the national school systems** and the related implications in the learning path of children of foreign origin. Based on this preliminary work, a training course for teachers was developed.

A second workstream focused on providing **administrative support and adequate information on the judicial implications of foreign minors’ access to education,** certificates acknowledgment, and participation in school activities. On the Regional Immigration Portal, an **online forum** was created and helped the development of a community of practice as it allowed the exchange of information, best practices, useful resources, and counselling among experts and professionals. Moreover, partners recovered, systematized, and updated all materials produced by local authorities to facilitate communication with foreign families and facilitate their access to some public services, making them available on the regional website.

⁷ Original title: In.Media.Res – Integrazione Mediazione Responsabilità

The main beneficiaries were students, parents, and the school staff. The latter, in particular, benefitted from meaningful help in the integration process of newly arrived migrant children, receiving training for the management of multicultural classes with the use of intercultural education, mediation, and ethnopsychological tools. These initiatives have then been replicated in other schools, and the project's recommendations and guidelines have sponsored the development of communities of practice.

Despite some difficulties in involving institutional partners, **the collaboration with the Municipality of Turin was fundamental**, especially for contacting schools and intercultural mediators, as well as for coordinating actions based on the needs of each school. Furthermore, at the final event, a Ministry of Education officer expressed his interest in the project and the possibility of replicating and standardizing it to higher levels, although the upscaling of this kind of intervention requires considerable financial resources.

“A legacy that this project has left to teachers and principals is the knowledge about where to look for information. Project materials and the forum are still accessible online and all partners have become a reference point at local level even beyond the end of the project” -
Manuela Spadaro, ASGI – Project Coordinator

Highlight

The project focused on the judicial implications of foreign minors' access to education, related in particular to enrolment requirements, the difficulties in the validation process and issuing of their school certificates – especially for students without residence permit – and the participation of undocumented students in school activities, such as trips. Legislation on these issues is quite complex as it is based on a jurisprudential interpretation, and there are no clear and specific laws, not even regarding the issuing of certification. In order to validate a certificate obtained in another country, students and their families have to provide proof that ratifies the validity and truthfulness of said certificate. Moreover, school principals continue exercising a certain level of discretion about the issuing of certificates, especially for undocumented children. To address these challenges, the project team worked to systematize laws, judicial decisions, and notes related to these issues in order to provide an efficient and effective information service for teachers and principals. A specific training was organized, and a legal counselling service was made available through telephone and in a dedicated space in the online Regional Immigration Portal.

Useful links and materials

Project website: <http://www.piemonteimmigrazione.it/mediato/i-nostri-progetti/scuola-e-formazione/2-non-categorizzato/169-inmediares>

Report "*Minori stranieri e diritto all'istruzione e alla formazione professionale. Sintesi della normativa vigente e delle indicazioni ministeriali (aggiornata con le Linee guida del MIUR del febbraio 2014)*"
https://asgi.it/wp-content/uploads/2014/05/1_0014_scuola_def_asgidocumenti.pdf

Video: <https://youtu.be/eljK2HAvYbE> and power point presentation:
http://www.piemonteimmigrazione.it/mediato/images/corsi/In_media_res.ppt Repaired.pdf

5.5 Journeys of Hope: Educational Pathways to Social Inclusion and Tolerance

The growing number of refugees, asylum seekers, and migrant children entering Europe places specific demands on schools and teachers. The future school population of the EU will indeed be increasingly characterized by multiple cultures and values, and teachers are expected to reconsider learning methodologies to meet the needs of these pupils and foster tolerance, respect for diversity, and civil responsibility throughout all school communities.

The aim of the Journey of Hope project was to foster social integration of people with disadvantaged backgrounds, to **promote intercultural dialogue, democratic values, and fundamental rights, non-discrimination and active citizenship, critical thinking, and media literacy**. This two-year Erasmus+ project was implemented from September 2016 until August 2018 in Greece, Italy, Spain, Turkey, and Austria. The Coordinator of the project was Öffentliches Stiftsgymnasium der Benediktiner zu St. Paul (based in Austria) and the consortium consisted of Liceo Scientifico Statale Filippo Silvestri, 4th High school of Ilion, Istanbul Lisesi and IES Joaquin Turina.

The target participants were upper secondary school pupils aged 15–18 years who became principal agents. Students were encouraged to experiment, try out and showcase their abilities, as well as broaden their horizons, experience the beauty of diversity, and build a better future for the European society.

*“The children very much enjoyed participating in activities themselves (...)
It was very beneficial for [them]” -
Leonidas Tourlas, Maths teacher,
responsible for the implementation of the
project in Greece, 4th High school of Ilion*

To provide new dialogue opportunities and exchanges of good practices and common values across borders, two groups of eight students from each school participated in **student exchanges** in other partner schools. Unfortunately, migrant students with temporary legal status did not have the right to be granted travel documents. Thus, they were unable to travel abroad and actively participate in the student exchange. Students were hosted by families, despite some reluctance in hosting foreign students due to language barriers and house inadequacy. At school, they were offered specific courses focusing on migration and were invited to participate in many activities to become familiar with the goals of the project. During the implementation, it was also noticed that **the socio-educational integration of migrant/refugee students was easier in schools with a small number of foreign students**.

Participants were also invited to find ways to show other students and teachers how to address the issue of racism and promote tolerance and inclusion. To this end, two study guides were created. The first was created by students for their peers and contained advice and tips in order to fight racism and discrimination. The second guide was created by participating teachers and is addressed to their colleagues. It encompasses the project’s best practices and proposes specific class activities to promote the inclusion of migrant/refugee students in the classes.

The project promotes a child-centred approach, where children and young people are key agents and beneficiaries with the chance to develop essential life skills. The added value is that teachers start perceiving the **well-being of students as an essential condition in the school**. During the project implementation, teachers started paying attention and listening to students’ opinions both in planning and in implementing activities.

In terms of reproducibility, partners are designing a new project called “Diversity and inclusion” which will start operating soon. Migrant and refugee students have already expressed their interest.

Highlight

Experiential activity, cooperation, communication, dialogue, and teamwork are key aspects of a successful youth and integration project. The Journey of Hope initiative demonstrated the importance of students having the chance to interact with students from other countries and spend time together at school, during field visits, and at home. Through contact with students, their families, and teachers from other countries, participating students were indeed able to observe different lifestyles, discover alternative mentalities and discuss cultural differences and similarities. Thus, they realized that there are always common points despite any differences and understood the principle of equality.

Useful links and materials

Deliverables are available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/projects/eplus-project-details/#project/2016-1-AT01-KA219-016660>

Facebook group: <https://www.facebook.com/IlionYouthGroup/>

5.6 L'AltRoparlante: Multilingualism and Translanguaging at School⁸

The project L'AltRoparlante promotes a “translanguaging turn,” which focuses on the necessity to **include in the curricular educational activities all languages and dialects belonging to students' individual and collective repertoires in the light of a multilingual learning approach**. Through the adoption of **translanguaging methodologies**, the linguistic repertoires and dialectic heritage of students are endorsed, thus improving the process of empowerment of bilingual students and de-constructing language hierarchies as well as culture-based stereotypes and prejudices, going a step beyond the sole “intercultural approach”.

Contrary to the mainstream approach of the Italian national school system, which promotes the teaching of Italian as a means of inclusion, this project works on the language of origin to improve the students' bilingualism and the related cognitive and linguistic advantages. Based on a **child-centred approach** that places the linguistic repertoire of the child at the core of the didactic planning, the project promotes **languages as a key factor of inclusion and a democratic tool**. Students feel equal and have the opportunity to express themselves freely in their own language.

The project is coordinated by the University for Foreigners of Siena (CLUSS Center) and is based on the experience of schools in the USA, Canada, and other European countries. After a first phase of piloting started in 2016, the project is being implemented in six schools in Italy (from kindergartens to middle schools), located in non-urban contexts and characterized by a high presence of diverse linguistic repertoires.

The project promotes a **bottom-up approach** starting with an in-depth analysis of the school's multilingual repertoire through informative preliminary meetings with school principals, teachers, students, and parents. Teachers are offered training on bilingualism and translanguaging as pedagogical praxis. Concurrently, children explore the association between their

“The project is more effective in territories where the school is still central to social cohesion. In these territories, the school is a powerful catalyst, families and the municipality as well trust its work and consider the project a positive initiative” -
Carla Bagna, Scientific referent of the project,
Director of CLUSS – University for Foreigners of Siena

“If you just conduct intercultural activities, culture may be transferred but it risks becoming a stereotype. If you work on the language, through the language, intercultural is transferred as well as the whole of what a person is, thus it is the deepest and truest form of inclusion” -
Sandra Martini, Teacher Primary School IC Marco Polo in Prato

languages and their emotions, and parents are informed of the advantages of bilingualism. A second phase includes the **co-design of translanguaging activities within the curricular learning path**. A common initiative is the “linguistic schoolscape” aimed at transforming the school environment into a pluralistic space with posters and boards translated into different languages.

To make the process effective, **working jointly and networking with teachers is a key element**. Teachers are offered periodic training and meetings with international experts to discuss translanguaging methodologies and

improve their professional skills. A thematic newsletter and periodic cross-school meetings further promote knowledge and best practices sharing. Additionally, teachers contributed to writing a book, including teaching materials and multimedia products, to promote various didactic activities and foster the replicability of the project. Similarly, the contribution of parents is essential. Parents actively participate in daily class activities

⁸ Original title: L'AltRoparlante: plurilinguismo e translanguaging a scuola

by reading short stories or translating words. This also fosters relations among parents and a sense of belonging and welcoming in the school.

The M&E process, through qualitative and quantitative assessments, demonstrated that the project favours the development of linguistic competences, and **promotes the awareness of children's own identity, eliminating any form of discomfort or shame in connection to their origins and the migration path of their family**. Moreover, the project allows for a rediscovery of both languages of origin and dialects. Thanks to the use of many languages, children become accustomed to a different resonance and develop their curiosity. In terms of narrative skills, tests revealed that students participating in translanguaging activities obtain a higher score on the meta-cognitive elements. The promotion of a multilingual repertoire reaches an extremely high level of inclusion, as well as facilitating the learning process of the Italian language within the class, thus avoiding the marginalization of linguistic minority groups. On the teachers' side, the project promotes a re-design of their role as they partially share their educational power with students and sometimes parents. This promotes sharing and trust, as well as children's empowerment.

Overall, the project has activated a positive domino effect across school levels and other schools. Moreover, it proves to be sustainable in the long term as teachers can become autonomous in the implementation of the approach, and specific financial resources are not required.

Highlight

The project offers many stories of the empowerment of children with a migrant background. Migrant children, in fact, often feel marginalized in the school environment and uncomfortable using their mother tongue or narrating the migration path of their families. This sense of discomfort and shame is overcome when the language repertoire of the child is positively rewarded. Translanguaging favours the transformation of the traditional relationship between teachers and students, as well as among peers, placing the child with his/her own linguistic and cognitive competences at the heart of the didactic planning. Migrant children are actively involved, and their linguistic repertoire becomes an added value for the class as a whole. Consequently, the child feels welcomed, speaks his/her mother tongue more frequently, participates more actively in class, and starts sharing with pride stories about the origins and the migration path of the parents. This promotes curiosity and enrichment for all students, which results in a strengthening of the interconnectedness among peers. The rediscovery of their language of origin simultaneously favours an intergenerational dialogue between children, grandparents, and relatives in the country of origin, strengthening relations across borders.

Useful Links and Materials

Website: <https://cluss.unistrasi.it/1/116/153/L-AltRoparlante.htm>

Evaluation: <http://www.erasmusplus.it/lingue/laltroparlante-didattica-plurilingue-nella-scuola-primaria/>

5.7 Municipal Coordination of Educational Opportunities for Newly Arrived Immigrants – as part of the Transfer Initiative Programme Family⁹

The aim of the Transfer Initiative Programme Family is to support and advance better-coordinated education management in districts and independent cities of Germany. Within the programme, one of the projects is the “*Municipal Coordination of Educational Opportunities for Newly Arrived Immigrants*,” which was launched in 2015. It focuses **on supporting cities and districts in setting up a regional education management system** in order to offer suitable educational opportunities for all citizens in all phases of life and to make them fit for the future. The aim is to **promote participation in education as the key to the social integration of new immigrants**. For this purpose, 321 independent cities and districts have been funded.

The methodology includes **needs assessment, mapping of landscapes, structures, and stakeholders within municipalities, interdisciplinary work and coordination, and the establishment of working groups**. In Leipzig, for instance, this assessment was carried out at local public enterprises, cultural institutions, and in the municipal administration, and allowed the strengthening of their network capability. In addition to intra-municipal networking, language schools and tutoring services, employment agencies, social welfare offices, socio-cultural centers, and community centers, volunteer agencies, NGOs, the Department for Migration and Integration, city sports associations, and community libraries were included in the work. In other cities, kindergartens and schools participated as well. In some cases, these synergies enabled structural integrations. For example, in Leverkusen, some members of the Steering Committee on Education were integrated into the Steering Committee of the Municipal Education Office in an advisory capacity. Moreover, coordinators with specific expertise were attached to different administrative offices or units to broaden the impact.

*"Education is more than formal education, it's about lifelong learning." -
Education Coordinator*

Overall, the project encourages **strong and sustainable synergies between the administration and civil society**. This is the case in Leipzig, where the short- and medium-term results also include a city symposium on Diversity in Cultural Institutions, a stronger focus on neighborhoods and coordination with the community work, the intercultural opening of city libraries, and further training for the administration and other institutions on diversification and intercultural competencies. Further, municipal offices receive thematic reports and a task report about sustainability, diversification, and qualification.

*"Education monitoring is a benefit for the entire education landscape." -
Education Coordinator*

The project places emphasis on **education monitoring** as an asset for the entire educational landscape because a strong data-based analysis can facilitate the argumentation for certain needs and, for example, can help to ensure that assistance is more targeted and tailored to the needs of the individual. In the city of Leverkusen, for instance, a project education report is used by politicians, administrators, and education stakeholders as a basis for discussion and decision-making. The school social index, which was developed in cooperation with the municipal statistics office, is also used within this scope.

Generally speaking, the project is highly transferable and expandable. In many municipalities, the programme was the first step towards data-based municipal education management, and data-based networking has become indispensable. The future extension of the project is feasible, and the funding enables a steady development throughout the communities involved. The programme is funded by the German Federal

⁹ Original title: Kommunale Koordinierung der Bildungsangebote für Neuzugewanderte

Ministry of Education and Research (and the European Social Fund of the European Union for the Transfer Agencies).

Highlight

Following from the networking initiative, the Afeefa Leipzig urban guide has been launched with the participation of the coordinators and following on from the analogue guide Leipzig Intercultural. The website provides a barrier-free and always up-to-date digital overview of all important offers and opportunities for newcomers at a glance, such as language courses, counselling on various topics, or leisure activities. In Leipzig, Afeefa is funded by the Department for Migration and Integration, the Digital Department, and the Social Welfare Office of the City of Leipzig. The platform is now available in Dresden, Leipzig, County of Leipzig, Bautzen, and the whole Thuringia region, and is available in German, English, Arabic, Farsi, and Spanish (in Thuringia, also in Russian, Bulgarian, Polish, French, Romanian, Kurdish, and Turkish). In Thuringia, the Institute for Vocational Education and Social Management (IBS) – a company of the Worker’s Welfare Thuringia - has been working together with Afeefa - Digitaler Zusammenhalt e.V. since mid-2021 to develop the platform "Afeefa - Colourful Compass for Thuringia. Search. Find. Join in."

Useful Links and Materials

Transfer Agency North-Rhine Westphalia

- Resource Collection: <https://www.transferagentur-nordrhein-westfalen.de/informationen/materialsammlung/>
- Practical Examples from the municipalities (Digitisation & Internal Cooperation): <https://www.transferagentur-nordrhein-westfalen.de/informationen/aus-den-kommunen/>
- Information Download Section: <https://www.transferagentur-nordrhein-westfalen.de/informationen/downloads/>
- Information on the new funding cycle and its focus: <https://www.transferagentur-nordrhein-westfalen.de/bildungskommunen/>

Afeefa

- <https://bunter-kompass-thueringen.info/athur>
- <https://afeefa.de/leipzig>

5.8 PARENTable – Communicating with Parents of newly migrated Children

The Project PARENTable builds on the experiences of the Erasmus Plus project ENABLE (2017-2019) aimed at co-creating with Arab teachers and tutors, a training for supporting refugee children in self-organized learning. The same consortium, composed by PH Schwäbisch Gmünd (Germany), University of Gävle, (Sweden), Muğla University (Turkey), Università della Calabria, (Italy), and Back On Track (Germany), is now implementing the Erasmus+ project PARENTable for the period 2019-2022. The core ambition of this initiative is to develop and implement a workshop concept in four countries (Germany, Sweden, Italy, Turkey), that brings parents, legal guardians, and teachers of refugee students together and empower both sides by training and mentoring.

National and local integration policies often propose immediate incorporation of newly arrived children into national schooling systems. However, educators, teachers, and the school staff generally lack adequate information about children’s family situation, their personal histories, and their educational path. In addition, parents are difficult to reach, especially when they do not speak the local language and lack trust in school authorities. Moreover, parents often do not understand their children’s challenges in terms of multiculturalism and identity formation in new settings. This prevents them from playing a positive role in supporting their children. To overcome these issues, the project aims to **build bridges between families of newly migrated children and schools, fostering mutual understanding and communication.**

To reach this objective, partners work to develop **an inclusive training concept** for both parents/legal guardians of newly arrived children and teachers based on ground-experience in five workshops in Germany, Sweden, Turkey, and Italy, organized between November 2019 and August 2022. The workshops, addressed to parents of migrated children and educators, focus on improving communication among them, starting from a **multidisciplinary perspective**, encompassing pedagogy, psychology, and cultural studies. Educators can thus better support newly migrated children between new school contexts, and parents can gain a deeper understanding of the challenges their children face and can also make their perspectives and needs to be heard at school. The project PARENTable believes indeed that parents **are one of the most important pillars for migrant children’s successful course of education and social inclusion.** The results of the interviews conducted Europe-wide will be edited and published as a handbook.

The project also provides for the **collection of best practices** of great parent-teacher-understanding in Europe, which will be incorporated into another handbook that will be passed on to educators, practitioners, and politicians.

Finally, based on the expertise of a transnational team, the project provides for the development and provision of an open-source **e-learning course** about subjects such as identities, migration and families, multilingualism, successful communication, and counselling. The online course is composed of 6 modules that give the possibility to learn about the needs of parents and educators.

“Parentable is a wonderful project that helps to make schools better places for all children. I am eager to learn more about parents’, children’s, and teachers’ experiences of communicating with each other, and I am looking forward to knowing more about their ideas on how to remove possible obstacles in the communication between schools and families.” - Prof. Daniel Rellstab, head of the MA program “Intercultural German Studies and Multilingualism”, University of Education Schwäbisch Gmünd (from the website).

The design of the project is highly sensitive to social, cultural, equity-oriented, participatory, and co-creation-design, as well as trauma-related conditions relevant to its target groups and other stakeholders. Further, the project has an established network of different professionals, such as academics (education, migration,

psychology and counseling, linguistics, cultural studies), teachers, educators, social workers, cultural mediators, and translators.

Highlight

The project has already shown its potential to be transferred to different contexts, even beyond Europe. The project partner Back on Track e.V., indeed, already used part of the prepared workshop materials in their own work with teachers of the learning centre of Homs League Abroad in Gaziantep/Turkey in March 2021. Feedback from the participating teachers was great: “You made us change our view on parents! We will certainly profit from this workshop and be more inclusive when it comes to parents’ needs and capacities!”.

Useful Links and Materials

Website: <https://www.parent-able.com/>

Facebook page: <https://www.facebook.com/enable.ph.gmuend>

5.9 Refugee Resettlement: Addressing Educational Needs of Newly Arrived Syrian and Iraqi Students in Ireland

Resettled refugees in Ireland have mostly been allocated social housing through local authorities participating in the Irish Refugee Resettlement Programme (IRPP). The aim of this Resettlement programme was to address the needs of newly arrived Syrian and Iraqi migrant families across a broad range of areas of support. It was executed in three locations in Ireland: Laois, (2015-2016), Limerick (2017-2018), and Wexford (2017-2019); and was funded by UNHCR and the Department of Justice in conjunction with County Councils, who outsourced the services to the NGO Doras Luimí. This NGO is a community-based organisation that promotes a holistic approach to children, considering their educational needs, their overall wellbeing, their family, and their ethnic and migration contexts.

Based on a **solid interagency approach** and grounded on an **effective community development approach**, the project had a wide remit in identifying holistic needs and developing appropriate interventions and learning to support the integration of newly arrived refugee families. The interventions were aimed at ensuring successful access and participation in education and bridging gaps in language competency and missed/interrupted educational pathways. Specific measures were put in place to support children and young people's integration in education, which included homework clubs and English language classes staffed by volunteer teachers, as well as a **buddy system** that was developed to support children's inclusion in school. In this way, the newly arrived Syrian and Iraqi children had a friend and possibly a confidant, providing a real grounded connection.

Children were also incentivized to join after-school clubs running locally, that intersected with their own interests, such as sports or music. To ensure that children and young people were involved in activities throughout the school holiday, the programme supported engagement with Easter Camps and liaised with youth groups and services to identify activities. Additionally, Doras Luimní's expertise on issues related to pre-migration, settlement, and post-migration, such as the possible trauma children can experience throughout their migration process, led to increasing **attention to participants' psycho-social needs and medical issues**.

“They have to build trust with people before they open up what they went through. And by the time when some of them open up you are finishing up. (...) We finished resettlement almost two years ago, but definitely they still come to us” -
Project Representative

Communication with schools was another important aspect of the resettlement support work. Beyond cultural mediators, **family advocates** recruited by Doras Luimní liaised with teachers and families to address the issues that children faced in school, raise awareness about difficulties faced by migrant families, and explain the Irish educational framework. This implied a lot of work with teachers and principals and involved discussions around academic standards, the purpose of education, and the **imperative of ensuring children's happiness at school**. Parents also benefited from **tailor-made integration plans** to support their integration into the community, based on the understanding of the heterogeneity of each family's needs and features.

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Drawing on the work and research undertaken, the NGO developed a **Refugee Resettlement Toolkit**: a resource that is now freely available and which provides support tools for specific groups, spanning all phases of the integration process. Additionally, research partners developed an integration and capacity building map which outlines the short-, medium-, and long-term goals of the project and identifies 12 integration indicators based on best practices identified in the UK and Europe.

The main impacts of the project are difficult to measure specifically, but can be seen in the children's demeanour and general well-being, as they felt more comfortable and welcomed at school. It can even be

understood through the changes in their accents and their uptake of local ways of speaking, and it can be felt in conversations with children and their families.

While a specific formal post-project evaluation was not carried out, each project built on the lessons learnt from the previous ones. The Department of Justice organised a conference at which Resettlement Support Workers met and thereafter self-organised a network to share and learn from one another's work. This proved to be a great forum for support and networking. Moreover, the funded projects provided an **exit plan**, i.e., an assessment of ongoing needs and essential criteria that guarantee the project sustainability both financially and over time.

Highlight

One intervention that facilitated inclusion and belonging, also stimulating the engagement of young people, was a human library intervention. This initiative was organised by a refugees' group as they wanted to develop a way to foster local understanding about the reasons why they were in Ireland. Doras Luimní's staff helped by linking the group with the library. A good number of teenagers and young people acted as 'human books': they met and shared with the public their stories to the extent that they were comfortable with. Through this intervention, they were able to build connections with the local community in a safe way.

Useful Links and Materials

Refugee Resettlement Toolkit: <http://doras.org/all-resources/resources-refugee-resettlement-toolkit/>

5.10 Saint John of God Lands of Lleida – Almacelles¹⁰

Sant Joan de Déu Terres de Lleida – Almacelles is a centre that, among its services, provides institutional foster care for unaccompanied minors (UAMs) aimed at their social, community, and labour integration. This centre belongs to the Hospital Order of St. John of God, which is one of the largest international non-profit cooperation organizations in the world. The project was implemented in 2018 as an emergency response to the huge number of arrivals of UAMs during the period 2015-2018 in the Catalonia region and has become, over the course of three years, main the center of the region (and the only one providing an emergency service). In April 2018, the centre opened a first Reception and Integral Care Centre to host UAMs. Here, minors **learn the language and enter formal education and vocational training to work on their autonomy and independence**. In October 2018, an Emergency Protection Centre was created as an entryway for UAMs to the protection system. To reinforce the transition to autonomy, in May 2019, an Assisted Flat Service was then established for young people aged 16 to 18. Currently, the centre helps more than one hundred young unaccompanied migrants.

It is a very complete and holistic project which accompanies unaccompanied young migrants in their way of becoming integrated into the host country at multiple levels. The principal objectives are to assist with obtaining legal documents, offer language and vocational training, and favour the children's incorporation into the labour market. In quantitative terms, each year, the number of services and projects carried out by the organization in the region of Lleida and oriented towards assisting unaccompanied minors has grown. The vast majority of the hosted children exit the system knowing the language, having obtained their legal documents, and having received professional training. Nowadays, thanks to the collaboration with companies from all over the region, most of them also quickly find a job, and employers tend to be extremely satisfied.

"Everyone the children work with has a clear final objective, so everyone is laying down bricks to build the same wall." - Marcos Febas, Director of the Emergency Service and Chief of the Youth Integration Area at SJDTL

"We are working to ensure that the project continues and is consolidated over time (...) I believe that our model is perfectly replicable." - Marcos Febas, Director of the Emergency Service and Chief of the Youth Integration Area at SJDTL

The most significant strength of this project resides in the **capacity to react to a fast-changing context and the adaptability to the needs of the target population**. The centre benefits from being part of a huge organisation and its long-term partnerships with public institutions and associations of employers. Thanks to this network, resources availability and opportunities for training and offering jobs have always been available. A **political dialogue** has been established with the Autonomous Government of Catalonia

and, more specifically with Lleida's provincial and local administration, which have recognized the successful contribution of the project to the society.

Created in an emergency context to act as a host system for UAMs, the centre did not carry out a systematic evaluation of its work. Nowadays, however, they plan to start developing their own reports. This will facilitate the reproducibility and transferability of the project and will favour the systematization of their work and the sharing of know-how.

¹⁰ Original title: Sant Joan de Déu Terres de Lleida – Almacelles

The project's next steps aim to promote a change in the institutionalised foster care to a more **individualised assistance led by the specific psycho-social needs of each case**.

The project is funded with governmental funds - Directorate General for Child Care (DGAIA) of the Department of Work, Social Affairs and Families (TASIF), and by the Foundation Sant Joan de Déu Terres de Lleida.

Highlight

Against the negative propaganda that is sometimes contained in the media's portrayal of unaccompanied minors, the organization tries to promote the dissemination of positive news to raise awareness in society and highlight the fact that these children are not criminals but studious individuals who are highly motivated to work. Indeed, recently 33 kids from their service obtained their vocational training certificate, news that was covered by the most important regional journal "Segre" to show that the stories of these children tend to be successful. Thanks to the work done by the organization, UAMs obtaining their diplomas and integrating into the labour market is the most common outcome.

Useful Links and Materials

Website: <https://www.sjd-lleida.org/>

5.11 SEDIN Project - Creative Methods for Successful Inclusion in Multicultural Schools

The Erasmus+ project SEDIN was implemented from December 2017 until February 2020 in Greece, Bulgaria, Belgium, Italy, Spain, and Turkey. The consortium consisted of NGOs, universities, education and vocational training centres, and state institutions.

The mainstream school environment of the host countries and the traditional cognitive teaching models are often inadequate to address the needs of refugee children and children with a migrant background. There is a growing need to **introduce in the school environment, in cooperation with different stakeholders, alternative methods that cultivate the children's imagination and that promote emotional aspects of learning and positive interaction** between migrant children and children belonging to the mainstream communities. To this end, SEDIN project aims at transferring and upscaling two educational methodologies for more inclusive classes: **the Montessori Method and the Creative Learning method**.

Both these methods are based on movement, creativity, cooperation, and non-verbal communication, and help the children enjoy the lessons and express their talents. Montessori is a method of education that is based on **self-directed activity, hands-on learning, and collaborative play**. In the SEDIN project, this method is taught through the Creative Learning method, which is based on the use of **theatre techniques** in order to stimulate learning in the classroom. The use of theatre techniques in primary school is indeed proven to be very effective for the improvement of children's school performance. The key principle is that children learn better when they actively participate in the learning process by comparison with being passive listeners. The improvement registered by the project has been significant: children, especially those with refugee, migratory, or minority backgrounds, who were shy, started to participate more, cooperate more in class increased and improve their educational performance.

To transfer this educational methodology, SEDIN project developed an **e-learning training** – an asynchronous online 40-hour course including relevant theory as well as practical examples. The e-learning course was addressed mainly to primary school teachers (more than 1,000 teachers from all over Greece enrolled in the course), especially in schools with a meaningful number of children from migrant and refugee backgrounds, and aimed to develop their skills in relation to the use of the Montessori Method and the Creative Learning Method. Based on the initial methodology developed by the project coordinator Action Synergy, teachers applied the methodologies in their classes by developing their own scenarios. Finally, they shared with the project team relevant reports regarding the implementation in class. The Regional Directorates of Elementary Education participated in the training and shared information with their members contributing significantly to the favourable implementation of SEDIN. Interestingly, the project showed that **the role of teachers is one of the most important elements for the successful integration of students**. This is especially true for Greece, where teachers can autonomously apply innovative methods in their classes.

“Teachers have fundamental role in creating a positive school environment”. - Konstantinos Diamantis - Balaskas, Project manager, Action Synergy

“SEDIN raised the children's self-esteem and cooperation in class” - Konstantinos Diamantis - Balaskas, Project manager, Action Synergy

The external evaluation assessed how well SEDIN met its objective of facilitating the improvement of the educational performance of refugee children and children with a migrant/minority background. Teachers implemented a wide range of Creative Learning and Montessori activities with a generally good degree of fidelity. The methods enabled teachers to develop pupils' social and learning skills as well as

curriculum content in ways that pupils found engaging. Group work and collaboration were common features across SEDIN classrooms, and cultural diversity was enhanced. Organisations and policymakers endorsed the SEDIN project as an appropriate and valuable methodology in schools.

Highlight

A new project originated from the SEDIN experience: MonTech project will foster social inclusion and equality in multicultural schools across Europe through highly innovative and engaging activities based on a new approach that blends the Montessori method with cutting-edge Maker Education learning experiences. The idea is to design a new approach that starts from a well-tested traditional method (Montessori) and adds EdTech methodologies (Maker Education and Creative Computing) with the double objective of adapting Montessori to the new context of multicultural schools and updating it with modern but affordable digital tools and methods for schools with few economic resources. The main objective of this project is to facilitate the social inclusion of children with refugee/migrant or minority backgrounds in their school environment.

Useful Links and Materials

Website <http://sedin-project.eu/>

Deliverables are available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/projects/eplus-project-details/#project/592253-EPP-1-2017-1-EL-EPPKA3-IPI-SOC-IN>

Full evaluation report: <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/project-result-content/5e461610-2df5-4900-8b3f-332d0932e5d9/SEDIN-FINAL-EVALUATION-REPORT.pdf>

Summary: <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/project-result-content/c67a5321-0322-4e4e-91c3-358ffce75e03/SEDIN-FINAL-EVALUATION-RPT-EXEC-SUMMARY.pdf>

5.12 SIREE - Social Integration of Refugees through Education and Self-Employment

Following the recent influx of refugees in Europe, the 2 Seas region (France, the Netherlands, England, and Belgium) is grappling with the challenges of integrating migrant families into both the educational and economic fabric. The regional school systems fail to correctly integrate the children, who are characterized by missed school years and confronted with a new education system. There is also a limited involvement of parents and insufficient support for teachers.

Co-funded by the European Regional Development Fund, the Interreg project “SIREE” contributes to the social and economic integration of refugees by **improving access to education and increasing their economic independence by stimulating self-employment through the method of co-creation**. It provides two independent work packages, one dealing with education, and the other dealing with employment. As regards the former, across the different partners’ countries, SIREE’s objective is to merge 40 new learning communities, resulting in more parental involvement in the children’s education, more children in school, a higher level of influx into adult education, and teachers who are better trained in supporting refugees. The **learning communities** were tested in Belgium, the Netherlands, and England and involved the school team and parents in primary schools and students and school teams in secondary schools. Participants had monthly meetings to facilitate dialogue about the specific challenges for schools and for the target groups and co-create ways to tackle these challenges. A toolbox has been created for educators with tools to be co-creatively used with students during the meetings.

“[It] was a really safe environment for them [children] (...) like the teachers, everyone was 100% involved, the relationship was so warm between everybody” - Miranda Poeze, Researcher, Centre of Expertise Social Innovation & Coordinator and lecturer minor Strong(er) Divers, VIVES University of Applied Sciences

The impact of the project has been positively evaluated through an **ad-hoc evaluation process**, encompassing in-depth interviews with participants and schools, and using scales based on pre-set indicators such as improving contact with parents, better student participation in school, and increasing the competencies of teachers. Generally, very positive responses are reported at the conclusion of the project, even despite the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. The project has shown to improve the relationship between parents and teachers. Moreover, school directors indicate that there is a change for many teachers in terms of attitudes and competencies. The dialogue, the learning about the culture of the parents and their domestic situation, and the understanding of the issues that immigrant children face, help teachers to better understand certain culturally sensitive topics and establish a communication channel in a safe space.

At the same time, the project relies on the voluntary engagement of schools, an aspect that is reported as a main obstacle, especially during the Covid-19 emergency, as schools are overburdened and are reluctant to take on voluntary projects. Nonetheless, the project has proven to have an overall positive impact and is potentially transferrable to any learning environment.

Highlight

The project reportedly improves relationships among teachers and parents, who are often hesitant and not sure if they are allowed to voice concerns within the school environment. Thanks to the project, informal dialogue is incentivized among families and school staff, which in turn improves trust. As a result, after a

few months, parents change attitudes and start bringing sensitive issues to the table while teachers better understand cultural concerns. With improved relationships, it is easier to address issues. For instance, in one participating school, the children didn't have separate changing rooms to prepare before the physical education class, and the boys and the girls had to do this together. The learning community discussed the reasons why this was problematic, the school understood the parents' concerns, and a solution was adopted. The cultural reasons were accepted and also shared by non-migrant families. This episode allowed teachers to understand that the parents often have similar worries and concerns regardless of their cultural background.

Useful Links and Materials

Website: <https://www.siree.eu/>

SIREE E-book and toolbox: <https://www.siree.eu/educators-toolbox>

Van Maele, D. and Poeze, M. (2018). *Transcending educational boundaries: challenges to the educational inclusion of refugees in Europe's 2 Seas area*. Kortrijk: Vives University of Applied Sciences

6 Takeaways for a Good Practice

The collection and analysis of 60 good practices across Europe provides an interesting overview of a meaningful set of socio-educational initiatives aimed at migrant and refugee children's integration in Europe. The wealth of contextualised data and cross-cutting features, together with the in-depth description of 12 selected case studies, displays a variety of inspirational, innovative, and effective initiatives that can shape ideas on how to best address the inclusion of children with a migrant background in European societies. Acknowledging the complexity and diversity of the contexts in which these projects were implemented, these findings also give valuable **food for thought to start reflecting on policy recommendations** addressed to the educational and policy sector and aimed at a political and educational change at the national and EU level.

To begin with, the dataset shows that the majority of initiatives aim at multiple goals according to the assumption that the socio-educational inclusion of children with a migrant background is interpreted and aimed at from different perspectives. This extreme multidimensionality mirrors the complexity of socio-educational integration processes, as also depicted in the IMMERSE dashboard of indicators, which identifies 5 areas and 14 outcomes of integration. This multidimensionality is reflected not only in the goals pursued by the analysed good practices but also in the numerous activities implemented, the various targets involved, and the diverse environments addressed. As a matter of fact, one single separate intervention cannot guarantee the successful attainment of socio-educational inclusion within our societies. Effective strategies focus, in fact, on a combination of factors and approaches that contribute to the level of impact of a project, implementing different workstreams and addressing not only a specific target with its needs but also the whole spectrum of actors that are involved in the process of inclusion at different levels. This approach fosters societal change, which is also pursued through an extension of the educational space beyond the traditional learning spaces, as well as the acknowledgement of educational environments as social hubs where migrant and refugee children develop social skills and important relationships. Drawing from this reflection, a first conclusion is that **policies and practices shall adopt a multidimensional approach that is able to mirror the complexity of the socio-educational integration process through a combination of activities, multiple targets, and extended spaces of intervention.**

A second reflection that can be drawn from the analysis concerns the different levels of intervention. The database includes a well-balanced combination of both small-scale initiatives, suited to fit the specificity of a given context or grounded in a community-based approach, and large-scale practices implemented at the European/international level. The socio-educational inclusion of migrant and refugee children is indeed a process that can be addressed from different perspectives, both essential to reach an effective impact and a balance between ad-hoc and standardized interventions. Different contexts and targets have different needs and, simultaneously, territories share similar challenges and the potential for mutual improvement through cross-border cooperation, access to a transnational pool of resources and social capital, and transferability of best practices. Therefore, we can conclude that **intervention models shall adopt a multi-level approach to properly and comprehensively foster the goal of inclusion.**

A holistic approach also requires the involvement of many **professionals from different areas of expertise** and the development of heterogeneous **partnerships and/or networks**, composed of governmental and local authorities, NGOs, school communities, universities, and research centres. Apart from educational practitioners who are key in the process of socio-educational inclusion, experts from other disciplines, such as research, mediation, psychology, law, etc., shall be part of the intervention model, as it clearly emerged in the previous analysis. The engagement of qualified experts is even more significant when professionals from different disciplines work jointly to create synergies and share common efforts. An interagency approach

contributes to the formation of a multi- and interdisciplinary community that provides adequate assistance, support, and guidance to the multi-faced process of inclusion. To sum up this point, a **multi-stakeholder, interdisciplinary and collaborative approach shall be considered in any policy and practice to ensure a high-level, qualified, and effective intervention.**

Another pertinent point that the in-depth case studies provide is a reflection about the experimentation of **innovative approaches to intercultural education** based on the adoption of an **integrated, tailor-made, empowering, and inclusive approach**, where migrant children are acknowledged as *agents* and the whole *community* is actively involved. Many projects try to re-design the educational environments, especially schools, to promote a more efficient model and space of socio-educational inclusion based on a child-centred approach. Migrant and refugee children are not passive actors, but, thanks to participatory processes, they are directly involved in the co-design and implementation of activities as key agents and co-authors of their educational and inclusion path. Fundamental to this approach is also the recognition of the specific needs of each child and the necessity of tailor-made interventions. To this end, new school governance and management structures are proposed, lifelong learning is promoted through training for school staff, and innovative teaching methods are applied. Moreover, the school opens its door to welcome collaborations with other professionals and build relationships with parents and the community. These experiences of social innovation and inclusive education have proven to be effective. For this reason, we can conclude that **policies shall systematize and capitalize on this know-how, favour the transfer of knowledge and the sharing of best practices to reinforce a common model of integration, based on a balance between standardization and flexibility related to specific needs, and favour the implementation of innovative practices in the field of education and social integration.** In connection to this last remark, it is important that practices adopt an efficient and effective evaluation, communication, and dissemination strategy to favour the reproducibility and transferability of good practices to similar and/or different contexts. To this end, **adequate funds and resources should also be allocated** to guarantee the sustainability of the projects, including beyond the formal conclusion, and investments should be addressed to guarantee the systematization of good practices.

Annex 1. List of 60 good practices

This annex provides the list of the 60 good practices identified by IMMERSE research partners, in alphabetical order. An extensive and accurate description of the initiatives is available on the [Online Digital Database](#), to be launched on IMMERSE website in May 2022.

- [Abraza África / Misión Emmanuel](#)
- [ALI MSNA – 1° VOLO - Linguistic literacy and access to education](#) (*original title: MSNA-ALI 1° Volo - Alfabetizzazione Linguistica e accesso all'istruzione*)
- [Barça Foundation FutbolNet program: Sports, Life Skills and Values for Unaccompanied Minors in Sicily, Italy](#)
- [Bookcase Programme – Promoting Language and Diversity](#)
- [Case Management Tool for Non-formal Education in Youth Work](#)
- [Centre for Children – Frouararcheio](#)
- [Children's Rights Schools North Rhine-Westphalia](#) (*original title: Kinderrehteschulen NRW*)
- [Competence Network Democracy Education for Young People](#)
- [Cork Migrant Centre Youth Group Support](#)
- [Creative Agency Programme at the Glucksman](#)
- [EDNIP - Embracing Diversity, Nurturing Integration, Learning for Life Project](#)
- [Egeria Program - For the inclusion of immigrant students in intercultural schools](#)
- [Enable-Tamkin - Self-Learning for Arab Refugee Children & Building a Concept for Mother-tongue Trainers & teachers](#)
- [FAMILIA – Migrant Families: Local Intervention of Active inclusion](#) (*original title: Famiglie Migranti: Interventi Locali di Inclusione Attiva*)
- [FRIDA Project - Training for the prevention and detection of racism and xenophobia in the classroom](#)
- [Groep Intro vzw](#)
- [HE.ST.I.A. Helping Students in Acceptance](#)
- [ICAM - Including Children Affected by Migration](#)
- [In Crescendo](#)
- [In.Media.Res – Integration Mediation Responsibility \(Integrazione Mediazione Responsabilità\)](#)
- [ItaStra – Italian Language School for Foreign Students at the University of Palermo](#)
- [J@M vzw Youth Work](#)
- [Journeys of hope: educational pathways to social inclusion and tolerance](#)
- [KAIRÓS MAJADAHONDA ASSOCIATION - Care and support for children and teenagers at risk of social exclusion and their families](#)
- [L'AltRoparlante: multilingualism and translanguaging at school](#) (*original title: L'AltRoparlante: plurilinguismo e translanguaging a scuola*)
- [Learning for Integration Project: Quality Learning and Non-Formal Education for Refugees and Migrant Children](#)
- [Learning to fly - learning workshop for all children](#) (*original title: Fliegen Lernen- Lernwerkstatt für alle Kinder*)
- [Migrant Teacher Project](#)

- MINT – Mentoring for Integration of third country national children affected by migration
- Multitasking Cooperative Classrooms (*original title: Aulas Cooperativas Multitarea*)
- Municipal Coordination of Educational Opportunities for newly arrived immigrants as Part of the Transfer Initiative
- Network of Teachers with a History of Migration (*original title: Netzwerk der Lehrkräfte mit Zuwanderungsgeschichte*)
- NEW ABC
- PARENTable
- Parents for all
- PERCORSI project - Training, work and integration of unaccompanied minors (*original title: Progetto PERCORSI - Formazione, lavoro e integrazione dei minori non accompagnati*)
- Platform Minors in Exile - Right to Education working groups (three)
- Progetto Su.Per. SUccesso nei PERcorsi formativi degli studenti di origine immigrata
- Project “Integral attention to children” - Tomillo Foundation
- Projecte Rossinyol – Intercultural youth mentoring programme in Spain
- Prollema - Empowering young migrants to teach their mother tongue
- RAA Berlin - Regional Work Centres for Education, Integration and Democracy e.V.
- RefuEdu – Exchange of knowledge and good practice to enhance the education of refugee and asylum seeking youth
- Refugee Resettlement: Addressing Educational Needs of Newly Arrived Syrian and Iraqi Students in Ireland
- RESTORE – Developing safer and positive school climate through restorative practices
- Rohingya Resettlement in Carlow, Ireland: Children’s Integration in the Wider Community
- Rucksack Schule - School Backpack - A programme for Language Education and Parental Education
- S.U.C.RE: Supporting University Community pathways for REfugees-migrants
- Sant Joan de Déu Terres de Lleida – Almacelles
- SARI - Soccernites, Hijabs and Hat Tricks and Diverse City by Sport Against Racism Ireland
- Schools of Sanctuary
- SEDIN Project – Creative Methods for Successful Inclusion in Multicultural Schools
- Serve Now
- SIREE – Social Integration of Refugees through Education and Self-Employment
- SIRIUS 2.0 Project (continuing the work of the SIRIUS Policy Network on Migrant Education)
- Stage Nederlands Voor Kinderen (4-12 Jaar)
- Step2School Education Programme
- Syrische Vrijwilligers
- Voisins Solidaires
- Waterford Integration Services - Engagements in Education

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